

Physico-chemical studies on mixed ligand complexes of Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with famotidine and some amino acids

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Abstract : Present study has been done on the mixed ligand metal complexes of Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with famotidine and amino acids. Mixed Ligand complexes of Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with famotidine as one ligand and glycine, leucine, valine or alanine as second ligand have been prepared. Keeping in view importance of famotidine as antiulcer drug and possible enhancement of its action due to the complex formation. The complexes have been investigated using different analytical technique such as elemental analysis, electronic and IR spectra and TGA and DTA techniques. All the complexes have octahedral geometry. Their thermal decompositions take place in two steps.

Keywords : Famotidine, mixed ligand metal complexes, amino acids, TGA/DTA.

Introduction

The mixed ligand metal complexes in which the ligands play different roles in biological systems and pharmaceutical industries are attracting wide attention of the researchers. Famotidine (fam) is a highly effective long acting histamine H₂ receptor antagonist^{1,2}. It has a high degree of specificity for the H₂ receptor, reduces the acid and pepsin content, as well as the volume of basal and stimulated gastric secretion. α -Amino acids are fundamental structural unit of proteins. The later perform diverse biological functions such as in regulation of metabolic processes, transportation of oxygen in body and catalyzing biological reactions. Keeping in view, the potential chelating tendency and their importance in biological and medicinal fields, it was thought expedient to synthesize their mixed ligand complexes with Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with famotidine as one ligand and glycine (gly), leucine (leu), alanine (ala) or valine (val) as second ligand. The complexes were characterized by elemental analysis, electronic, IR spectra and TGA and DTA thermal technique.

Experimental

Preparation of the complex : The metallic salt, fam

and gly/leu/val/ala were taken in the stoichiometric ratio 1 : 1 : 2 so that the total weight was about 1–1.5 g. The metallic salt was dissolved in 50 ml of distilled water; the ligands were added slowly into the solution of the metallic salt with continuous stirring. The pH was maintained ~9.0 by adding ammonia solution. The matrix was refluxed for nearly two hours on a water bath. On concentrating and cooling, the complex separated out which was filtered, washed and dried in desiccator.

Physical measurement : The metal content in the complexes were determined following standard methods. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated in Micro Analytical Lab. Nitrogen contents were determined by Kjeldh's method. Sulphur was estimated by messenger method.

Electronic spectra were run on Beackan DU-64 spectrophotometer in nujol mull and IR spectra on Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer using KBr pellets. TGA and DTA curves were recorded on thermal analyser station Redcroft STA-780 series with a sample size of 2–6 mg, heating rate of 10 °C/min in air atmosphere with a flow rate of 60–70 ml/min.

Results and discussion

On the basis of the metal estimations, the mixed ligand

metal complexes have been assigned the composition as given in Table 1. The complexes are insoluble in water but moderately soluble in carbon tetrachloride.

In the IR spectra of famotidine (Fig. 1) two bands

appearing at 1350 and 1180 cm^{-1} are assigned due to stretching vibrations of $\nu_{\text{S}=\text{O}}$. These bands are shifted to lower wave number showing the coordination of oxygen of S=O bonded in the metal³. Also, two bands appearing at 3250 and 3150 cm^{-1} are assigned due to $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ (asym)

Table 1. Physical characteristics of mixed ligand metal complexes

Complex	Colour	Decomposition temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Found (%)				
			Metal	C	H	N	S
[Mn(fam)(gly) ₂]	Brown	215	10.7	26.4	4.1	21.7	15.6
[Fe(fam)(gly) ₂]	Dark brown	220	11.1	25.8	3.8	21.6	15.2
[Co(fam)(gly) ₂]	Brown	225	11.2	25.8	4.1	22.9	16.2
[Ni(fam)(gly) ₂]	Brown	240	10.8	26.1	3.8	23.0	17.0
[Mn(fam)(leu) ₂]	Brown	190	9.1	35.8	5.4	17.4	13.5
[Fe(fam)(leu) ₂]	Dark brown	215	9.0	34.2	5.3	18.9	13.2
[Co(fam)(leu) ₂]	Dark brown	220	10	35.1	5.5	18.5	12.9
[Ni(fam)(leu) ₂]	Dark brown	235	11.2	34.8	4.9	18.4	13.8
[Mn(fam)(val) ₂]	Brown	195	8.1	33.6	4.2	19.9	14.6
[Fe(fam)(val) ₂]	Dark brown	215	8.8	33.7	4.5	18.8	14.3
[Co(fam)(val) ₂]	Brown	230	10.4	32.9	3.9	18.6	14.8
[Ni(fam)(val) ₂]	Brown	240	10.0	34.0	5.0	18.8	13.8
[Mn(fam)(ala) ₂]	Brown	210	9.9	25.3	3.4	21.2	15.3
[Fe(fam)(ala) ₂]	Dark brown	215	10.8	27.8	3.6	21.3	14.6
[Co(fam)(ala) ₂]	Brown	235	10.7	28.2	3.2	21.5	14.3
[Ni(fam)(ala) ₂]	Brown	245	10.3	27.9	3.3	21.2	15.6

Fig. 1. IR spectra of famotidine.

Note

and ν_{N-H} (sym) vibrations respectively (Table 2). In the IR spectra of each amino acid three bands around 3260, 3100 and 1500 cm^{-1} are assigned to ν_{N-H} (asym) and ν_{N-H} (sym) and δ_{N-H} vibrations respectively⁴⁻⁶. In the mixed ligand metal complexes (Fig. 2) ν_{N-H} absorption bands are observed in the form of broad bands in the range 3220–3060 cm^{-1} which may be resulting from the shifting (due to complex formation) of ν_{N-H} bands of famotidine as well as ν_{N-H} bands of amino acids. The

band due to ν_{COO} (asym), ν_{COO} (sym) of carboxylic group are observed in the region 1620 and 1400 cm^{-1} in the free ligands. Bathochromic shift of these bands in all the cases shows the coordination of oxygen with the metal. The absence of ν_{OH} of the carboxylic group appearing at 2600 cm^{-1} in free ligands confirms the deprotonation of OH bond by coordination⁷. Complex formation is further confirmed by the bands⁸ found in the complex at 500–570 and 360–460 cm^{-1} due to M–N and M–O bonds.

Table 2. Important IR bands (cm^{-1}) of mixed ligand complexes of famotidine and leucine

Sl. no.	Compound	$\nu_{\text{S=O}}$ (fam)	$\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ (fam)	$\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ (leu)	ν_{COO} (asym)	ν_{COO} (sym)	$\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ (COOH)	$\nu_{\text{M-O}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-N}}$
1.	Famotidine	1350 (asym) 1180 (sym)	3250 (asym) 3150 (sym)	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	Leucine			3260 (asym) 3100 (sym) 1500 (δ)	1620	1400	2600	-	-
3.	[Mn(fam)(leu) ₂]	1305 (asym) 1135 (sym)		3185 (asym) 3060 (sym)	1610	1415	-	415	520
4.	[Fe(fam)(leu) ₂]	1315 (asym) 1145 (sym)		3190 (asym) 3070 (sym)	1600	1420	-	420	540
5.	[Co(fam)(leu) ₂]	1320 (asym) 1150 (sym)		3200 (asym) 3075 (sym)	1550	1420	-	425	570
6.	[Ni(fam)(leu) ₂]	1342 (asym) 1170 (sym)		3205 (asym) 3080 (sym)	1560	1415	-	410	570

Fig. 2. IR spectra of Co-fam-leu complex.

From the electronic spectral bands it is inferred that all the complexes have octahedral geometry as Mn^{II} ⁹ show four bands in the range 30400–30660, 29100–29220, 24200–24300 and 12600–12800. Fe^{II} ¹⁰ one band at 12600–12860, Co^{II} ¹¹ three bands at 9200–9360, 15460–15600 and 26460–26620 cm^{-1} and Ni^{II} ¹² three bands at the range 8460–8660, 16900–17100 and 24400–24500 cm^{-1} .

TGA curves of mixed ligand metal complexes (Fig. 3) indicate that they decompose in two steps. The decomposition ranges of the steps and percentage weight loss are given in Table 2. The first step decomposition corresponds to the loss of two molecules of the amino acid (gly/leu/val/ala) and the second step decomposition corresponds to the loss of fam and formation of metal oxides. In case of Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{II} complexes, the weight of metal oxide corresponds to formation of Mn_3O_4 , Fe_3O_4 , Co_3O_4 respectively while in case of Ni^{II} , NiO .

Kinetic parameters such as apparent activation energy and order of reaction for the 1st step thermal decomposition of Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes have been determined by graphical methods of Coats and Redfern¹³. The values of kinetic parameters are given in Tables 3

Table 3. Kinetic parameters of mixed metal complexes of famotidine with amino acid

Sl. no.	Complex	Order of reaction	Activation energy (kJ mol ⁻¹)
1.	[Mn(fam)(gly) ₂]	1	4.3
2.	[Fe(fam)(gly) ₂]	1	4.5
3.	[Co(fam)(gly) ₂]	1	4.6
4.	[Ni(fam)(gly) ₂]	1	4.8
5.	[Mn(fam)(leu) ₂]	1	3.2
6.	[Fe(fam)(leu) ₂]	1	3.4
7.	[Co(fam)(leu) ₂]	1	3.5
8.	[Ni(fam)(leu) ₂]	1	3.6
9.	[Mn(fam)(val) ₂]	1	3.4
10.	[Fe(fam)(val) ₂]	1	3.6
11.	[Co(fam)(val) ₂]	1	3.7
12.	[Ni(fam)(val) ₂]	1	3.9
13.	[Mn(fam)(ala) ₂]	1	4.0
14.	[Fe(fam)(ala) ₂]	1	4.1
15.	[Co(fam)(ala) ₂]	1	4.7
16.	[Ni(fam)(ala) ₂]	1	5.0

and 4. In each case the first thermal decomposition has the order of reactions as 1. The activation energy values follow the order with respect to metal $\text{Mn}^{\text{II}} < \text{Fe}^{\text{II}} < \text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$.

Fig. 3. TGA curve of Zn-fam-gly complex.

Table 4. TGA data of the complexes

Complex	1st decom. temp. (°C)	% weight loss		1st decom. temp. (°C)	% weight loss		Activation energy (kJ mol ⁻¹)
		Obsd.	(Calcd.)		Obsd.	(Calcd.)	
[Mn(fam)(gly) ₂]	215–265	26.4	(27.4)	320–370	41.8	(42.3)	4.3
[Fe(fam)(gly) ₂]	220–270	25.9	(27.3)	325–375	41.9	(42.8)	4.5
[Co(fam)(gly) ₂]	222–275	26.5	(27.2)	330–380	43.5	(44.2)	4.6
[Ni(fam)(gly) ₂]	240–280	26.6	(27.2)	335–385	43.4	(44.1)	4.8
[Mn(fam)(leu) ₂]	190–240	38.7	(39.9)	285–335	34.9	(35.0)	3.2
[Fe(fam)(leu) ₂]	215–265	38.6	(39.8)	310–360	34.2	(35.4)	3.4
[Co(fam)(leu) ₂]	220–265	38.7	(39.6)	320–365	35.2	(36.7)	3.5
[Ni(fam)(leu) ₂]	235–275	51.3	(39.6)	325–380	35.1	(36.6)	3.6
[Mn(fam)(val) ₂]	195–235	36.2	(37.1)	310–355	35.0	(36.6)	3.4
[Fe(fam)(val) ₂]	215–260	36.0	(37.1)	315–365	36.3	(37.0)	3.6
[Co(fam)(val) ₂]	230–275	34.8	(36.9)	320–370	39.8	(38.3)	3.7
[Ni(fam)(val) ₂]	240–280	34.6	(36.9)	325–375	39.7	(38.2)	3.9
[Mn(fam)(ala) ₂]	210–260	30.5	(31.0)	315–360	40.0	(40.2)	4.9
[Fe(fam)(ala) ₂]	215–265	30.6	(31.0)	320–365	40.1	(40.7)	4.1
[Co(fam)(ala) ₂]	235–270	30.0	(30.0)	325–370	41.9	(42.1)	4.7
[Ni(fam)(ala) ₂]	245–285	30.2	(30.8)	330–375	42.0	(42.0)	5.0

DTA curves of Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} show two peaks (peaks temperatures as given in Table 5) which are exothermic in nature. 1st exothermic peak is due to the liberation of two molecules of amino acid while the second peak is assigned due to simultaneous decomposition

Table 5. DTA data of the complexes

Complex	1st exothermic peak	ΔH of 1st exothermic peak (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	temp. (°C)	
[Mn(fam)(gly) ₂]	265	2.7
[Fe(fam)(gly) ₂]	270	3.0
[Co(fam)(gly) ₂]	280	3.2
[Ni(fam)(gly) ₂]	285	3.4
[Mn(fam)(leu) ₂]	210	2.0
[Fe(fam)(leu) ₂]	215	2.1
[Co(fam)(leu) ₂]	217	2.3
[Ni(fam)(leu) ₂]	220	2.4
[Mn(fam)(val) ₂]	230	2.1
[Fe(fam)(val) ₂]	240	2.3
[Co(fam)(val) ₂]	245	2.5
[Ni(fam)(val) ₂]	250	2.6
[Mn(fam)(ala) ₂]	240	2.4
[Fe(fam)(ala) ₂]	245	2.6
[Co(fam)(ala) ₂]	248	2.7
[Ni(fam)(ala) ₂]	255	2.8

and oxidation reduction process of the complex. The values of heat reaction for first exothermic thermal transition have been calculated by the method given by Borchadt and Daniels¹⁴ and the same are given in Table 5. From the value of the heat of reaction it is observed that the order with respect to metal is Mn^{II} < Fe^{II} < Co^{II} < Ni^{II}.

On the basis of elemental analysis, IR and electronic spectra and TGA and DTA studies, the following structure can be assigned to the metal complexes.

where M = Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II}

R = H/CH₃/CH(CH₃)₂/CH₂CH(CH₃)₂

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